

Sonia Marques,
Edja Trigueiro

À la recherche de la maison moderniste perdue

Introduction

The modernist house from a paradigmatic view to Brazilian adaptations

As is widely known, housing was at the core of thoughts and debates involving the pioneers of the Modern Movement in Europe, at the CIAMs, and particularly in the achievements of German architects involved in large scale housing programmes based on *machine à habiter* or *existenz minimum* concepts. In the US, whereas housing experts (i.e. Bauer and Mumford) emphasised the European movement original principles as tied to social purposes, the Modern Movement was being presented (Hitchcock & Johnson, MoMA 1932 exhibition) as a new style – *the International Style*. The divorce thus produced between architecture – a matter of style – and housing – a social issue – has, as is here believed, contributed to restrict the fuller modernist experience to a few European countries or to the experiments of *avant-garde* groups scattered around the world. Despite national differences and the pervasiveness of traditional exterior models it can be said that modernity brought about dramatic changes within the home. An instance of that is the alteration in the articulation of the social and the service spheres in Europe as well as in North America, by pulling kitchens to the focus of the domestic scene. Early symptoms of this process in British houses in the aftermath of World War I have been demonstrated in an earlier study (Trigueiro, 1997). It is argued here that in Brazil modernity did not go beyond the masters' social sphere (Marques, 1994).

Modernism à brasileira

In Brazil the ubiquitous acceptance of the modernist formal repertoire not only overwhelms the

scenery even of old town cores but often mutilate individual built shells in their former colonial/eclectic integrity, with added modernist bits and pieces in a sad 'frankenstinian' fashion. This *look of modernity* – with its geometrical volume composition, stripped surfaces, horizontal windows and fake flat roofs – goes little beyond skin surface, its true face being unveiled in the realm of domesticity which constitutes, in some aspects, quite the reverse of what had been prescribed in the early modernist discourse of the twenties. Although the emergence of certain spatial articulations identified in this study points towards changing ways of life, the recurrence of patterns found in pre-modernist homes suggests that space is organised to reproduce old types of interface among the communities of home users – masters, visitors and the others.

Research 1: of masters, visitors and the others

Data and analytical tools

Twelve house plans randomly selected from a database being organised by UFRN architectural students make up the modernist sample. These cases – built from the 50's to the 70's, when the modernist formal repertoire disseminated throughout Brazil – are analysed and results compared to pre-modernist examples investigated in previous studies. Observations of key formal features and layout organisation are fine tuned by the investigation of their spatial structure through the application of syntactic analysis.

The way essential functions relate to one another and to all others in a building lie behind the notion of *genotype* defined as the "... *abstract rules underlying spatial forms*." (Hillier & Hanson, 1984:12) These rules can be retrieved from a plan by a set of analytical techniques of which graph representation (*access graphs*) and numerical measurements (*integration values*) are used in this study. Access graphs are matrixes of interconnected spaces in a building with each space represented by a dot and their links by lines, as shown in figure 1b. Computer applications calculate each matrix so to translate topological aspects into numerical values. Integration values – the measurement to be referred here – express how each space articulates with all others in the complex. Lower to higher values make up a scale from more integration to more segregation.

When spaces that accommodate certain functions relate to the complex in a consistent pattern or numerical order across a sample there are reasons to believe that the graphic/numerical expression of a socio-cultural pattern – a genotype – has been revealed (Hanson, 1992). The identification of genotypical patterns of integration among the main dif-

ferent domestic functions may be viewed as the conceptual foundations in this attempt to decipher the soul of the local modernist home.

Of shapes, layouts, orientation and social interface

Three types of layout associate with certain built shells that, albeit not exhausting the repertoire available at each period, represent colonial, eclectic and modernist dwellings.

The front room, alcoves-plus-corridors, back room-plus-kitchen layout of one-volume, side-gabled terraced houses (figure 1) has conquered archetypal status in historiography as they dominated the built environment up to the last quarter of the nineteenth century and still function as landmarks for older town cores. The front-core-back layout, associates with day-night-day activities and with inhabitants-visitors (mainly male), inhabitants-inhabitants, and inhabitants-servants (mainly female) modes of interface.

Despite their diverse built shells the late nineteenth/early twentieth century, multi-volume, highly-ornamented, detached eclectic houses (from French neo-classical to Brazilian neocolonial through Alpine chalets and Victorian villas – fig. 2) present a recurrent layout of two distinct sequences of cells (most intercommunicating), one of day rooms, the other of bedrooms along a central axis. Terrace/porch, visitors room, dining room, servery/daily meals (copa), kitchen and service lobby form the day room sequence with the main dining room dominating the layout in the centre; outbuildings for servants are the norm. They encapsulate two modes of articulation: (1) one that can be referred to as of *lateralité* (as found for Normandy farm houses by Hanson et al, 1999), with day and night activities developing in spaces located at different sides along a central axis; (2) another of the front-back type, with the front day rooms accommodating the interface of inhabitants-visitors (adult family members of either sex), and the back day rooms accommodating that of inhabitants-servants.

More or less faithful to the international style formal repertoire (fig. 3) the layouts of detached, semi-detached and even terraced modernist houses (as these manifested in all settlement types), characterise mainly by being subdivided in sectors – social, service and private – which have inspired the notion of ‘the sector’s paradigm’ (Amorim, 1999). These are orientated primarily to meet environmental requirements with the ‘noble’ sectors – social and private – being privileged (figures 4, 5, 6 and 7). The private sector of bedrooms no longer intercommunicate, being mostly dead end cells, whereas servants quarters albeit usually built under the same roof, do not

link to any other part of the building except through the kitchen. Social cells still bridge the outside and the other sectors, thus keeping their traditional double roles of functional and transitional spaces, but the connections to the bedroom quarters are often permeated by halls and passages.

Of configuration and interfaces: from the repertoire

Elsewhere (Trigueiro, 1994) the space configuration of fifty colonial and eclectic houses were syntactically analysed. Three predominant configuration aspects emerged as highly suggestive of genotypical patterns in both sets: (1) the visitors’ room and the master bedroom are strategically positioned in configurational terms by locating closer to the main entrance, benefiting from alternative accesses and being highly integrated (lying *shallow* and on a ring in the access graph rooted from the street, and in the integrating side of the scale of integration values); (2) all service-related spaces, including the kitchen, are very segregated, do not lie on rings and are only accessible by means of various other spaces; and (3) the street is very segregated but the addition of alternative entrances plays a decisive role in altering patterns in some colonial and most eclectic houses.

By comparing graphs rooted from the street through the front door with graphs reworked to account for alternative entrances (fig. 1), distinct patterns appear to encode distinct types of interface: in some cases the integration hierarchy was altered and differences in integration reduced, in others nothing changed. The flexible version associates with suburban colonial houses and predominates among eclectic houses whose most integrated room is usually the dining room whereas the version in which the structure remained unaltered associates with inner town colonial dwellings whose most integrated space is the male-dominated front room. Such results reinforce the notion of the urban colonial *sobrado* of the mid-nineteenth century as the highest expression of Brazilian patriarchal society (Freyre, 1981) and the departure from that model in the early decades of the twentieth century.

The pervasiveness with which the master bedroom and the visitors’ room retain their integrating and controlling properties concerning all other spaces are evidences of continuity in the interfaces between the master – and later also the mistress – and the rest of the household. On the other hand the role played by dining rooms – the female-orientated, out-of-sight back room of colonial houses and the highly integrating central focus of social display in the 20’s – highlights the fact that be it the visitors’ or the dining room, the focus of integration in colonial as well as eclectic houses is the social sphere,

closed to women in the former orchestrated by women in the latter.

Of configuration and interfaces in modernist houses

Of the twelve modernist plans investigated most (8 cases) display the sequence visitors' room, dining room, kitchen with the house entered through the front door, as found in pre-modernist houses; either the visitors's or the dining room is the most integrated functional space (five cases each) as happened to pre-modernist houses; the street or the maids' room is the most segregated space (seven and five cases, respectively), as found for previous homes. (Figs. 4, 5, 6 and 7; tables 1 and 2)

On the other hand, the addition of alternative entrances does not alter the hierarchy of integration in five cases, generates only minor shiftings in the integration scale in five others and, surprisingly, sends the kitchen down the integration scale in two.

Some changes in the configuration of modernist homes as relates their pre-modernist counterparts point toward the reverse of what had been expected to have happened had Brazilian homes evolved towards informality and easy of movement as often prescribed in the modernist discourse of the twenties. The new requirements for privacy severed the 'private sector' from the rest of the house and turned formerly communicating bedrooms into dead end cells, often self-contained with their en suite bathrooms. However, this apparently reverse outcome reveals the contours of our own modernity as it signals the slackening of parental authority and a tendency for selective, occasional episodes of co-presence among dwellers which recent syntactic analysis (Holanda, 1999) seems to confirm. The apparent contradiction between increasing demands for privacy and enlarged social sectors - with added terraces, 'varandas' and 'pergolas' - seems to associate more with the need for status display than with expectations of a richer social life at a time in which a growing middle class was rapidly turning urban. However, this issue has not been satisfactorily investigated here and demands further studies.

On the other hand the segregating character of service-related spaces inherited from colonial, through eclectic, to modernist houses - in which kitchens alter little and maids' rooms remain as segregated as slaves' quarters of colonial times - is in itself a measure of the limits of our modernity.

Research II: current dwelling modes: any news?

Data and method of investigation

In the research 'Novas Formas de Morar', currently in progress, selection follows the identification of dwellers' status. Conditions associated with

the post-modernity, as extensively referred in the literature, are privileged: individual dwellers, such as single parent families, home-based working family heads, restructured families, etc. Observations and open surveys help to reveal how the house is being used, and identify conspicuous or inconspicuous conversions that may indicate transformations regarding previous arrangements.

Reorganising public and private within the home: keeping the 'hard core'

Some aspects of present day housing which manifest visibly in the built environment and seem to associate with new domestic requirements suggest a reenactment of modernist proposals (i.e. the shrinking of service-related space) whereas others point towards a setback from them (enclosed semi-private communal areas strongly detached from the public space), and others, still, signal towards the emergence of novel themes (the home-based office).

In the twelve cases observed so far, changes in the previous design features are almost non-existent. They do happen, however, in significant degrees in the ways space is used and this fact points towards a loss of significance of the social sphere - represented by the duet living and dining room - even when they retain their traditional arrangement in the home. Nobody seems to entertain in one's houses or flats. Reception spaces have been transferred to semi-private mezzanines and reception areas of apartment buildings or to 'reception houses' that multiply in most towns. Dining rooms have been substituted by the public premises of self-service canteens and restaurants in or around work places, where most people have lunch and often dinner. Kept as sacred icons, dining rooms are seldom used as gathering places for household members and/or visitors at one same time. Bedrooms in the so-called private sector tend to become whole houses in themselves with en suite bathrooms and a series of facilities such as TV/video/sound systems, fridges, computers and the like. The inhabitant/vehicle ratio increases. Service-related spaces, however, remain as a segregated 'hard core' in the fashion of the great majority of pre-modernist and modernist houses. The argument is illustrated by three instances of recently built apartment flats in Natal.

a) In middle-class 'Plano Cem' apartment complexes (Loureiro & Marques, 1999), kitchens and service areas amalgamate, and there is no maid's room, but a common bathroom and toilet facilities on the ground floor. The designer assumed that maids/nannies would be occasional workers. Actually, adaptations such as a hammock hanging in the kitchen as a sleeping arrangement for the ubiquitous maid are being introduced. On the opposite side, large common leisure areas are very success-

ful for barbecues and sport and as substitutes for dining and living rooms as pointed above.

b) In contemporary upper class dwellings three main differences from modern Brazilian standards appear on new designs or conversions: (1) the proliferation of en suite bathrooms; (2) of garages and (3) of reception halls inside communal areas.

c) Finally, a recent conversion of an upper class apartment into a 'potiguar' loft (Teles, 1999), revealed the presence of a social sector fashioned after New Yorker lofts (Riley, op.cit) alongside that of the same good old, immutable 'hard core' that signals the continuity of social relations based on low paid working class.

Conclusion

The international resonance conquered by the Brazilian modern architecture was essentially indebted to public buildings and formal aspects. Plastic dare may also be found in housing alongside outdated building technologies, not examined in this study, and especially alongside evidences of a contradictory face of our modernity, or of our missed-out modernity, that do not seem resolved in the present day. Thus, despite similarities between some social enclaves in Brazil and the post-industrial western world in terms of '... current demographic patterns, the shifting boundary between private and public realms, and new concepts of work and leisure ...', as stated recently in the MoMA exhibition 'The Un-private House' (Riley, 1999), novel domestic space designs have not as yet emerged and our *recherche pour une modernité perdue* seems reenacted.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amorim, L.M.E. (1999). 'The sectors' paradigm: a study of the spatial function and nature of modernist housing in Northeast Brazil'. Doctoral thesis, University College London.
- Hanson, J. (1992). 'Tradition and Experimentation in Housing and Neighbourhood Design' in *Proceedings of Prospects on Housing Policy and Technology Development for the 21st Century*, Korea, pp.139-186.
- Hanson, J. (1998). *Decoding homes and houses*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hillier, B. & Hanson, J. (1984) *The social logic of space*. Cambridge University Press.
- Holanda, F. (1999). 'Sintaxe de uma casa-átrio moderna', paper presented at DOCOMOMO, São Paulo, mimeo.
- Loureiro, C e Marques, S. (1999). 'Morar novo, cenário antigo', paper presented at ANPUR, Porto Alegre, mimeo.
- Marques, S. (1994). 'Arquitetura Brasileira. uma pós/modernidade mais do que contraditória', paper presented at ANPOCS, Caxambu, mimeo.
- Teles, V.M.M. (1999). 'O grau de satisfação e as mudanças ocorridas no condomínio Leonardo da Vinci', Specialisation Final Work, Natal, UFRN

Trigueiro, E.B.F. (1994). 'Change and continuity in Domestic Space Design: a comparative study of nineteenth and early twentieth century houses in Britain and Recife, Brazil'. Doctoral Thesis, University College London.

Trigueiro, E.B.F. (1997). 'The dinner procession goes to the kitchen' in *Proceedings of the First International Space Syntax Conference*, UCL-Space Syntax Laboratory, London, 2, 18.1-18.14.

KEYWORDS

Modernist house, Change and continuity, Space configuration

Sonia Marques. Architect (UFPE, Recife, 1973), Master Degree in Sociology (UFPE, Recife, 1983), Doctor Degree in Sociology, Ecole des Hautes-Etudes, Paris. 1996). Lecturer at: Departamento de Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFPE (1976-1997); Mestrados de Desenvolvimento Urbano: Sociologia; e Historia, UFPE (1996); Mestrado em Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFBA, Salvador (1997-1998); Departamento de Arquitetura, UFRN (1998-to present); Mestrado em Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFRN (2000).

Edja Trigueiro. Architect (UFPE, Recife, 1978). Specialist Degree in Sociology. (UFPE, 1986); Master Degree in History (UFPE, Recife, 1990); PhD (Bartlett School of Graduate Studies, University College London, 1995). Lecturer at: Departamento de Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFRN (1985-to present); Mestrado em Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFRN (2000); Vice-coordinator of the Programa de Pós-graduação em Arquitetura e Urbanismo, UFRN (1999-to present).

Source: Trigueiro, E. B. F. (1994). "Change (and continuity) in domestic space design". Doctoral thesis, UCL.

Fig. 1 – Access graphs of colonial sobrados

- D – Dining room
- V – Visitor's room
- T – social Terrace
- K – Kitchen
- B – Master bed
- Cp – "Copa"

Source: Trigueiro, E. B. F. (1994), "Change (and continuity) in domestic space design", Doctoral Thesis, UCL

Fig. 2 – Eclectic houses

RUA DO MOTOR

Source: Araújo, B. C. D. et al. (1999) "Estudo morfológico de exemplares modernistas na Praia do Meio", Coursework, UFRN.

RUA ADAUTO CÂMARA

Source: Macedo, L. (1999). "Estudo morfológico de uma edificação modernista", Coursework, UFRN.

RUA HENRY KOSTER

Source: Galvão, V. C. et al. (2000) "Levantamento histórico das edificações", Coursework, UFRN.

RUA OLIVEIRA GALVÃO (2)

Source: Dantas, U. C. (2000) "Arquitetura modernista: um exemplar em Natal".

RUA JUNDIAÍ

Source: Rodrigues, A. (1999) "Platibanda azul", Coursework, UFRN

RUA PINTO MARTINS

Source: Guedes, A. A. et al. (1999) "Estudo morfológico", Coursework, UFRN.

AV. SILVIO PEDROSA

Source: Bulhões, T. et al. (1999) "Estudo morfológico de uma edificação modernista em Natal", Coursework, UFRN.

Fig. 3 – Some modernist houses investigated

RUA JUNDIAÍ
 Source: Rodrigues, A. (1999)
 'Platibanda azul', Coursework, UFRN

RUA 25 DE DEZEMBRO
 Source: MELO, L. F. G. °; et al. (1999). "Estudo de edificações modernistas na Praia do Meio", Coursework, UFRN.

RUA ADALTO CÂMARA
 Source: Macedo, L. (1999). "Estudo morfológico e levantamento de uma edificação modernista, Coursework, UFRN

- | | | | |
|---------------------|--------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| transition
space | V – Visitors' room | Cp – Copa | Md – Maid's bedroom |
| | T – social Terrace | K – Kitchen | Ex – Exterior |
| | D – Dining room | B – master Bedroom | St – Street |
| | | | |

Fig. 4 – Built shells, floor plans and access graphs

RUA PADRE LEMOS

Source: MELO, L. F. G. O, et al (1999). "Estudo de edificações modernistas na Praia do Meio", Coursework, UFRN

RUA JOAQUIM MANOEL

Source: Ribeiro, L. M. (1999). "O estilo modernista na residência natalense", Coursework, UFRN.

RUA OLIVEIRA GALVÃO

Source: Dantas, U. C. (1999). "Arquitetura modernista: um exemplar em Natal.", Coursework, UFRN

from street thru' front door

from plot thru' all doors

Key to room functions

● transition space	V – Visitors' room T – Social Terrace D – Dining room	Cp – Copa K – Kitchen B – master Bedroom	Md – Maid's bedroom Ex – Exterior St – Street
--------------------------	---	--	---

Fig. 5 – Built shells, floor plans and access graphs

RUA OLIVEIRA GALVÃO (2)
 Source: Fonseca, G.M.C. et al. (2000)
 'Levantamento de edificações no bairro de Tirol',
 Coursework, UFRN

RUA HENRY KOSTER
 Source: Galvão, V.C. et al. (2000)
 'Levantamento histórico das edificações',
 Coursework, UFRN

RUA PINTO MARTINS
 Source: Guedes, A.A. et al. (1999)
 'Estudo morfológico', Coursework, UFRN

Key to room functions

● transition space	V – Visitors' room	Cp – Copa	Md – Maid's bedroom
	T – social Terrace	K – Kitchen	Ex – Exterior
	D – Dining room	B – master Bedroom	St – Street

Fig. 6 – Built shells, floor plans and access graphs

RUA SILVA JARDIM
 Source: Pinheiro, M.H.(1999)
 'Vila Ferroviária – Rocas', Coursework, UFRN

RUA DO MOTOR
 Source: Araújo, B.C.D. et al.(1999)
 'Estudo morfológico de exemplares arquitetônicos modernistas na Praia do Meio', Coursework, UFRN

AV. SILVIO PEDROSA
 Source: Bulhões, T. et al. (1999) "Estudo morfológico de um residência modernista em Natal", Coursework, UFRN

from street thru' front door

from plot thru' all doors

Key to room functions

	V – Visitors' room	Cp – Copa	Md – Maid's bedroom
transition space	T – social Terrace	K – Kitchen	Ex – Exterior
	D – Dining room	B – master Bedroom	St – Street

Fig. 7 – Built shells, floor plans and access graphs